

**19th International Conference on Chemistry
and the Environment - ICCE 2025**

Environmental Chemistry for Sustainability

E-Book of Abstracts

Belgrade, Serbia, June 8-12, 2025

19th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment ICCE 2025
Belgrade 8-12 June 2025

E-book of Abstracts

Published by

Serbian Chemical Society

Karnegijeva 4/III, 11000 Beograd, Srbija

tel./fax: +381 11 3370 467; www.shd.org.rs, E-mail: office@shd.org.rs

For Publisher

Melina Kalagasidis Krušić, president of Serbian Chemical Society

Editors

Ivana Ivančev-Tumbas, University of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences, Serbia

Vladimir Beškoski, University of Belgrade - Faculty of Chemistry, Serbia

Editorial Board

Thomas Bucheli, Environmental Analytics, Agroscope, Switzerland

Adrian Covaci, University of Antwerp, Belgium

Ester Heath, Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia

Antonio Marcomini, University Ca' Foscari of Venice, Italy

Maria Eduarda Pereira, University of Aveiro, Portugal

Slavica Ražić, EuChemS Executive Board Member; University of Belgrade, Serbia

Christian Zwiener, University of Tuebingen, Germany

Prepress

Research and Development Centre of Printing Engineering, Belgrade

ISBN 978-86-7132-088-7 (pdf file)

All the scientific content within this E-book of abstracts is licensed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this chapter are included in the chapter's Creative Commons license, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the chapter's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. Author(s) retain copyright and may enter into the separate, additional contractual arrangements for non-exclusive distribution of their work.

All rights for advertisements, visual identities and logos are reserved.

The information and the opinions given in this publication are provisional. Serbian Chemical Society, EuChemS Division for Chemistry and Environment, EuChemS, Editor and Editorial Board are not responsible for any interpretations, their consequences or typographical errors.

Scientific Committee

Patrik Andersson, Umeå University, Sweden
Tatjana Anđelković, University of Niš, Serbia
Vladimir Beškoski, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Thomas Bucheli, Environmental Analytics, Agroscope, Switzerland
Bogusław Buszewski, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland
George Cobb, Baylor University Waco, Texas, United States of America
Adrian Covaci, University of Antwerp, Belgium
Tatjana Cirković-Veličković, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Willem de Lange, Environment Agency Groningen, the Netherlands
Annabel Dias Barrocas Fernandes, University Beira Interior, Portugal
Philippe Garrigues, University of Bordeaux, France
Ester Heath, Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia
Krisztián Horváth, University of Pannonia, Hungary
Ljubiša Ignjatović, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Hideyuki Inui, Kobe University, Japan
Ivana Ivančev-Tumbas, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Begoña Jiménez, Instituto de Química Orgánica General, CSIS, Spain
Branimir Jovančičević, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Roland Kallenborn, Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Norway
Ioannis Katsoyiannis, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece
Jaana Koistinen, University of Helsinki, Finland
Perihan Binnur Kurt-Karakus, Bursa Technical University, Türkiye
Silvia Lacorte Bruguera, Department of Environmental Chemistry, IDAEA-CSIC, Spain
Gerhard Lammel, Max Planck Institute for Chemistry, Germany
Carlos Lledo-Fernandez, Robert Gordon University, United Kingdom
Snežana Maletić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Antonio Marcomini, University Ca' Foscari of Venice, Italy
Costas Michael, University of Cyprus, Cyprus
Vladimir Mihailović, University of Kragujevac, Serbia
Takeshi Nakano, Osaka University, Japan
Jasmina Nikodinović-Runić, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Stefan Panglisch, University Duisburg-Essen, Germany
Maria Eduarda Pereira, University of Aveiro, Portugal
Valery Petrosyan, Lomonosov State University, Moscow, Russian Federation, Russia
Bojan Radak, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Jelena Radonić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Slavica Ražić, EuChemS Executive Board Member; University of Belgrade, Serbia
Aleksandar Sabljčić, Ruđer Bošković Institute, Croatia
Michaela-Dina Stanescu, University POLITEHNICA Bucharest, Romania
Teresa Steininger-Mairinger, BOKU Wien, Austria
Ivana Teodorović, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jan Tříska, University of South Bohemia, Czech Republic
Aleksandra Tubić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Christian Zwiener, University of Tuebingen, Germany

City of Novi Sad ambient air: Aromatic hydrocarbons (BTEX) associated health risk

S. Bobić¹, Lj. Torović^{1,2}, N. Dragić^{1,2} and S. Bijelović^{1,2}

¹ Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

² Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

stanka.bobic@izjzv.org.rs

City of Novi Sad, the second largest city in the Republic of Serbia, occupies an area of about 700km² and has over 360,000 inhabitants with a large car fleet of about 200,000 vehicles (statistical data from 2023) [1]. As the road traffic is one of the major sources of air pollution and the inhalation exposure to aromatic hydrocarbons can cause adverse effects on human health, the current study assessed presence of benzene, toluene, ethyl benzene and xylenes (BTEX) in the ambient air of the City of Novi Sad, as well as associated health risk.

For that purpose, a total of 714 air samples (24h) obtained on two sites monitored in the City of Novi Sad during 2023 were subjected to GC-MS analysis of BTEX.

The overall percentage of the samples with quantified amounts of BTEX compounds was rather high: toluene 94.7% > xylenes 91.4% > benzene 90.2% > ethylbenzene 68.9%. In case of benzene, the higher mean concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) was recorded at suburban-traffic site (1.3 vs. 1.00), and in case of other BTEX compounds at urban-traffic site: 0.6 vs. 0.8 for ethylbenzene, 2.3 vs. 4.3 for toluene, and 2.0 vs. 3.2 for xylenes. When further averaged over all monitoring sites, BTEX were arranged in the following concentration order ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$): toluene 3.3 > xylenes 2.6 > benzene 1.2 > ethylbenzene 0.7. The annual concentration of benzene in the City of Novi Sad in 2023 is in accordance with calendar year limit value issued in Directive 2008/50/EC [2], while no limit values are prescribed for the other compounds.

The non-carcinogenic risk [3], presented as hazard index (HI) obtained as a sum of hazard quotients related to reference inhalation concentrations of BTEX compounds, was very similar on suburban-traffic and urban-traffic site (0.064 and 0.067), with overall mean at 0.066, indicating no health risk. Combined contribution of benzene and xylenes to HI was more than 98% (with contribution ratio of 2.1 and 1.1, in favor of benzene, on suburban- and urban-traffic sites, respectively). The carcinogenic risk [3], based on benzene and ethyl benzene inhalation risk units, was very similar on suburban- and urban-traffic site in case of children, 1.6E-06 and 1.5E-06, and in case of adults slightly higher on suburban- traffic site, 6.6E-06 vs. 5.8E-06, indicating low risk. In comparison with ethyl benzene, benzene showed 7-fold higher impact, due to both higher exposure and higher inherent carcinogenic potential.

Due to rapidly urban development of the City of Novi Sad, the number of inhabitants is growing and thus the number of vehicles is also increasing in the coming years, special attention should be paid to air quality management.

References

- [1] Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, ISSN 0354-4206, Retrieved from: <https://www.stat.gov.rs/en-US/publikacije/publication/?p=15431>
- [2] European Commission. (2008) Directive 2008/50/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2008 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe. Official Journal of the European Union, L152, 1-154.
- [3] USEPA.IRIS Assessments. https://iris.epa.gov/AtoZ/?list_type=alpha (2017) Assessed 16 Apr 2023.